

Creating the Climate Justice Dictionary — A Step-by-Step Guide

Based on the IPCC Assessment Report Six and Europe PubMed Central Open Access Literature Repository Using #semanticClimate Data Processing Software Tools

Abstract

The step-by-step guide is based on an experiment carried out by the #semanticClimate team, which focused on searching and computationally retrieving the open access scholarly research corpus from Europe PubMed Central (6.9 million open access papers) as well as all 70 chapters of the IPCC Assessment Report Six held on GitHub as HTML with IDs. The outcome of this experiment is a first-round scoping exercise to create the Climate Justice Dictionary, which represents terms associated with climate justice collected from this open scholarly corpus over 20 years as well as from the IPCC report.

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Authors

Simon Worthington – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8579-9717>

Renu Kumari – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9451-7814>

Peter Murray-Rust – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3386-3972>

Gitanjali Yadav – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6591-9964>

Shweata Hegde – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8258-274X>

Parijat Bhadra – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-2551-0293>

#semanticClimate <https://semanticclimate.github.io/p/en/>

The Climate Justice Dictionary:

Climate Justice Dictionary (work in progress): [Words_all_climatejustice.txt](#)

Climate Justice Dictionary (Wikipedia enhanced): [as web page](#)

Resources used

- Data processing software tools
- Dictionaries
- Literature corpora and semantified copies
- Annotation and indexing resources

Data processing software tools

Below is a table of the open-source software for data processing used by #semanticClimate for the literature analysis (Table 1).

Software

A full list of all #semanticClimate software can be found on [GitHub](#) (#semanticClimate 2019b) and on the #semanticClimate [Zenodo community](#) (#semanticClimate 2019a).

Name	Description	Code	Support
pygetpapers	Searches and downloads articles from repositories. Standalone, but the results may be used by “docanalysis” or possibly “pyamiimage.” Can be called from other tools.	https://github.com/etermr/pygetpapers	https://pygetpapers.readthedocs.io/
amilib	It is a Python library designed for document processing and dictionary creation. Python library of ami software especially NLP, HTML, downloading, and related convenience utilities “amilib” has tools for finding, cleaning, converting, searching, and republishing legacy documents.	https://github.com/etermr/amilib	README
Py4ami (bundled in amilib)	Translation of “ami3(J)” to Python. Processes CProjects* to extract and combine primitives into semantic objects. Some functionality overlaps with “docanalysis” and “pyamiimage.” Includes libraries (e.g., for Wikimedia) and includes prototype GUI in Tkinter, and a complex structure of word dictionaries covering science and related disciplines. (Note the project is called “pyami” locally but there is already a PyAMI project, so there it is called “py4ami.”)	https://github.com/etermr/pyami	README
pyamihtml (bundled in amilib)	Conversion of documents to styled HTML	https://github.com/etermr/pyamihtml	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CF68Fw9NytnUH2

			ZAEcpUeligXczhn4A/edit
docanalysis	Ingests CProjects and carries out text analysis of documents, including sectioning, NLP/text mining, vocabulary generation. Uses NLTK and other Python tools for many operations, and spaCy, ScispaCy for annotation of entities. Outputs summary data, correlations, word dictionaries. Links entities to Wikidata.	https://github.com/petermr/docanalysis	README
pyamiimage	Ingests figures/images, applies many image processing techniques (erode-dilate, color quantization, skeletons, etc.), extracts words (Tesseract), extracts lines and symbols (uses sknw/NetworkX), and recreates semantic diagrams (not finished)	https://github.com/petermr/pyamiimage	README
Dictionaries	Collection of Wikidata-based dictionaries for scientific annotation and searching	https://github.com/petermr/dictionary/	General: https://github.com/petermr/dictionary/ Creating dictionaries: https://github.com/petermr/tigr2ess/blob/master/dictionaries/TUTORIAL.md
amilib	IPCC Glossary download Code: https://github.com/petermr/pyamihtml/blob/main/test/test_headless.py	https://github.com/petermr/semanticClimate/tree/main/ipcc/ar6/test/total_glossary/output	https://github.com/petermr/amilib/blob/main/test/test_headless.py
amilib	IPCC/AR6 chapters download Code: https://github.com/petermr/pyamihtml/blob/main/test/test_headless.py	https://github.com/petermr/amilib/tree/main/test/resources/ipcc/cleaned_content	https://github.com/petermr/amilib/blob/main/test/test_headless.py

*CProject is a Corpus Project. This is the name for configuration, initialization, and storage of a literature search and analysis project.

Table 1. Software for data processing used by #semanticClimate

Dictionaries

The dictionaries are used for searching and annotating the literature corpora.

- Carbon cycle dictionary

https://html-preview.github.io/?url=https://github.com/petermr/amilib/blob/main/temp/dictionary/climate/carbon_cycle.html

- AR6/WG1/Chap03 dictionary
https://html-preview.github.io/?url=https://github.com/semanticClimate/JEP-article/blob/main/data/wg1chap03_dictionary.html
- Various dictionaries created at time of the COVID-19 pandemic: country, disease, drug, npi, organization, test_trace, virus, Zoonosis
<https://github.com/petermr/dictionary/tree/main/openVirus20210120>

Literature corpora and semantified copies

Two corpora are used in the research: Europe PMC and the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). First, Europe PMC is used as it is a key open academic aggregator and repository. The literature repository holds a significant amount of open access (OA) articles mainly in the bio sciences: 6.5 million with 47.7% of total articles in 2023 being OA as opposed to only 10% being OA when the service started in 2005 (Europe PMC 2024; see Figure A1). Additionally, Europe PMC has encouraged preprints since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, which enables early access to research papers and to cutting-edge science. Europe PMC provides articles as full text as well supports a wide range of computational machine access. The #semanticClimate community is able to carry out automated search and document retrieval using its software “pygetpapers.” Searches can target specific paper parts, such as abstracts, findings, or conclusions, and retrieval of papers can be as full text JATS format.

Figure 1. Europe PMC [percentage open access](#)

IPCC Sixth Assessment Report

The second resource used was the UN Climate literature corpus for the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), including its associated glossary. “The IPCC prepares comprehensive Assessment Reports about knowledge on climate change, its causes, potential impacts and response options” (IPCC, n.d.-a). The IPCC reports are the gold standard for climate science and policy, and their importance for understanding and addressing climate change cannot be overemphasized. As UN Secretary-General António Guterres has stated, “it is a survival guide for humanity. As it shows, the 1.5°C limit is achievable. But it will take a quantum leap in climate action. This report is a clarion call to massively fast-track climate efforts by every country and every sector and on every timeframe. In short, our world needs climate action on all fronts—everything, everywhere, all at once” (United Nations 2023).

AR6 is produced over several years, known as the Assessment Cycle, and consists of a number of reports made by working groups, including a synthesis report, working group reports, and special reports.

Sixth Assessment Cycle Reports and IPCC Glossary

- **Synthesis Report (SYR)** (Standalone end of Assessment Cycle report)
 - [Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report](#). Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. DOI: 10.59327/IPCC/AR6-9789291691647 (not open licensed) (Calvin et al. 2023)
 - [IPCC Glossary](#) (AR6 and Assessment Report 5 [AR5]): IPCC, 2023: Annex I: Glossary (Calvin et al. 2023) and on the IPCC website. DOI: various (not open licensed) (IPCC 2011)
- **Working Group reports** (these feed into the Synthesis Report)
 - [Climate Change 2021—the Physical Science Basis](#). Working Group I Contribution to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. DOI: 10.1017/9781009157896 (CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0) (IPCC 2023a)
 - [Climate Change 2022—Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability](#). Working Group II Contribution to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. DOI: 10.1017/9781009325844 (CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0) (IPCC 2023b)
 - [Climate Change 2022—Mitigation of Climate Change](#). Working Group III Contribution to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. DOI: 10.1017/9781009157926 (CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0) (IPCC 2023c)
- **Special Reports** (these feed into the Synthesis Report)
 - [Global Warming of 1.5°C](#). IPCC Special Report on Impacts of Global Warming of 1.5°C Above Pre-industrial Levels in Context of Strengthening Response to Climate Change, Sustainable Development, and Efforts to Eradicate Poverty. DOI: 10.1017/9781009157940 (CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0) (IPCC 2022b)
 - [Climate Change and Land](#). IPCC Special Report on Climate Change, Desertification, Land Degradation, Sustainable Land Management, Food Security,

and Greenhouse Gas Fluxes in Terrestrial Ecosystems. DOI: 10.1017/9781009157988 (CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0) (IPCC 2022a)

- [The Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate](#). Special Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. DOI: 10.1017/9781009157964 (CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0) (IPCC 2022c)

Unlike the research papers in Europe PMC, the AR6 is not published in compliance with modern open science and FAIR principles. Not all reports are open access, it is not available as full text, it is not held in a single open scientific literature repository, and it does not provide computational machine access. It is worth noting that the working group's data publication is different from the report that has been published; data are being published following modern open science methods, using Git versioning and FAIR principles. The #semanticClimate community has made semantified copies of the AR6 *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report* and IPCC Glossary using its software tooling, including [70 chapters of AR6](#) as annotated HTML with IDs per paragraph (work in progress) (#semanticClimate, n.d.) and the [IPCC Glossary](#) AR6 and AR5 as HTML and as linked open data in Wikibase (Willighagen and Willighagen 2023).

Annotation and indexing resources

The following from the Wikimedia technical ecology and linked open data resources has been used for annotating literature. Annotation in this context refers to adding additional information, for example, from Wikipedia and Wiktionary, or as “semantic labeling” with linked open data from Wikidata. Using these annotations the following features were enabled: definitions, multilingual definitions, image illustrations, and linked open data information, among others. The #semanticClimate tooling can access these resources via API access, scripting its tools in Jupyter Notebook, and so forth.

- Wikipedia: <https://www.wikipedia.org>
- Wiktionary: <https://www.wiktionary.org>
- Wikidata: <https://www.wikidata.org>

Work program in detail

A literature review/search for the term “climate justice” using the Europe PMC repository: A how-to

Key: Courier font denotes the #semanticClimate software name being used in the process; Bold courier font denotes commands; yellow boxes are commands; blue boxes are outputs.

Link to the [Jupyter Notebook](#) “Climate Justice Demo #semanticClimate Tools” running on Google Colab.

Complete work program on [GitHub Discussion](#), [GitHub Project \(Issues\)](#), and the [Jupyter Notebook](#) “#semanticClimate Tools” (Bhadra et al. 2024).

The Jupyter Notebook contains an executable version of the code for this section and can be used to re-run the process as described below or as a template for performing new term searches.

A literature review on a term is essential before doing any research on the topic. There are many publications released every day and saved on academic repositories. The tools listed below are used to retrieve the articles from academic repositories.

Note: The literature search tooling has to carry out this work retrospectively, either annotating the documents or adding them to a knowledge graph. Under the new publishing model being proposed, electronic publications would be produced in this way from the start (Stocker et al. 2024).

The following are the descriptions for retrieving articles and extracting information from them. This has been divided into three sections:

- A. Searching literature using a query term with `pygetpapers`
- B. Creating tables using [DataTables](https://datatables.net) (<https://datatables.net>) for the retrieved articles with `amilib`
- C. Extracting entities (e.g., COUNTRY) from the literature with `docanalysis`

A. Literature search for the term “climate justice” with `pygetpapers`

`pygetpapers` is a #semanticClimate tool to search literature from the Europe PMC scholarly literature repository and other repositories. It makes requests to open access scientific text repositories, analyzes the hits, and systematically downloads the articles without further interaction.

Figure A2 illustrates the steps to use for `pygetpapers`.

Figure 2. Steps to search literature from Europe PMC (Graphviz [source file](#))

Step 1: It can be installed using the following code in the terminal:

```
pip install pygetpapers
```

Step 2: The query term is added in the double quotes in the code mentioned below with following considerations. For example:

- The query can be limited to search within the specific time period with addition of a start date and end date.
- The use of `-n` will give the number of articles without any download of data.

```
pygetpapers --query '"climate justice"' --xml -n --startdate  
"2010-01-01" --enddate "2024-10-31" --output fin_climate_justice -  
-save_query
```

This code will search Europe PMC for open access scholarly literature on the term “climate justice” for the specified time frame.

Output:

```
INFO: Total number of hits for the query are 870
```

Step 3: The limit to download the data for the desired numbers can be added in the code to get the data for the required number of papers. It is done by removing `-n` and adding `--limit` followed by the number in the code.

Here we will call the downloaded papers the corpus.

```
pygetpapers --query '"climate justice"' --xml --limit 100 --  
startdate "2010-01-01" --enddate "2024-10-31" --output  
fin_climate_justice --save_query
```

Output:

```
INFO: Total Hits are 870  
  
WARNING: Could not find more papers  
  
100it [00:00, 194541.00it/s]  
  
INFO: Saving XML files to  
/content/fin_climate_justice/*/fulltext.xml  
  
100% 100/100 [01:42<00:00, 1.03s/it]
```

B. Creating tables using jQuery DataTables for the corpus with `amilib`

The corpus created for scholarly literature on climate justice is summarized in the form of tables using DataTables software. The important metadata of the corpus are given below.

- `pmcid`
- `doi`

- title
- authorString
- journalInfo.journal.title
- pubYear
- abstractText

These are steps to create tables using DataTables software from the scholarly literature corpus using the tool `amilib`.

Step 1: It can be installed using the following code in the terminal:

```
pip install amilib
```

Step 2: Create jQuery DataTables for the corpus.

```
amilib HTML --operation DataTables --indir fin_climate_justice
```

This code will create DataTables for the number of articles received for the term “climate justice.”

C. Extracting entity (COUNTRY) from the scholarly literature corpus using `docanalysis`

`docanalysis` is a tool that can extract specific entities from the corpus such as the countries appearing in the articles.

The tool can be installed using the code:

```
pip install docanalysis
```

Once the tool is successfully installed, `docanalysis` can be used to extract entities such as COUNTRY from the corpus. The list of countries are extracted from the specific section of the articles using `--search_section` (Key: INT = Introduction; RES = Result; CON = Conclusion; DIS = Discussion).

```
docanalysis --project_name fin_climate_justice --make_section --
search_section INT, RES, CON, DIS --dictionary COUNTRY --output
fin_climatejustice.csv
```

Results:

A. The tool `pygetpapers`

`pygetpapers` has been used to search literature on climate justice per three-year period over a 20-year span (Table A2). The results are not all “publications on climate justice” but papers retrieved in a conventional search for the term “climate justice.”

Start date	End date	No. of papers with term “climate justice”
------------	----------	---

2004-01-01	2006-12-31	0
2007-01-01	2009-12-31	0
2010-01-01	2012-12-31	4
2013-01-01	2015-12-31	20
2016-01-01	2018-12-31	37
2019-01-01	2021-12-31	235
2022-01-01	2024-10-31	574

Table 2. Comparison of publications on climate justice from 2004 to 2024, by three-year span

The table shows that there was no publication mentioning climate justice published from 2004 to 2009. From 2010 onward, the publication of articles mentioning the term “climate justice” has increased exponentially.

B. jQuery DataTables: Summary of the retrieved articles

A data table has been created for the articles published from 2010 to 2024 that mention climate justice (Figure A3). It presents a summary of all the retrieved articles, gives links to PMCID and DOIs, and also provides a brief abstract. DataTable supports the “human-in-the-loop” semi-automated part of the literature search in which the researcher can get a [condensed view](#) of search results and, for example, see all the journal names.

pmcid	doi	title	authorString	journalInfo	journal.title	pubYear	abstractText
PMC10021356	10.1371/journal.pgph.0001304	Achieving climate justice, safeguarding planetary health: Diagnosis and demands from next generation leaders for COP27 and beyond.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guinto RR • Deivanayagam TA • Chuji PT • Singh A • Taomia BKE. 		PLOS global public health	2022	
PMC10042626	10.1515/mopp-2021-0071	Climate Justice and the Duty of Restitution.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Truccone-Borgogno S. 		Moral philosophy and politics	2023	Much of the climate justice discussion revolves around how the remaining carbon budget should be globally allocated. Some authors defend the unjust enrichment interpretation of the beneficiary pays pr
PMC10063200	10.1016/s0140-6736(23)00276-3	No climate change justice in lieu of global authorship equity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riaz MMA • Wangari MC • Mugambi JK. 		Lancet (London, England)	2023	
PMC10122113	10.1016/j.lana.2023.100494	Climate change: we must act now to secure a sustainable, healthy future for all.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Lancet Regional Health- Americas. 		Lancet regional health. Americas	2023	

Figure A3. Data table for retrieved articles (list of 100 sample articles from 2010–24; [URL link to the data table](#))

C. The list of countries mentioned in the scholarly literature corpus

The names of countries mentioned in the papers were extracted with `docanalysis` and represented in a word cloud (Figure A4), in which the size of the word depends on how frequently the word is mentioned in the corpus of 100 articles published from 2010 to 2024. At present in the scoping exercise, only cleaned-up data have been retrieved and presented; false positives have been removed, to a degree. The next step would be for a researcher to theorize why certain countries are mentioned more frequently than others in relation to the topic of climate justice.

Figure 5. The list of IPCC reports and chapters that include the term “climate justice” ([Graphviz source file](#))

From the IPCC corpus, we found that many chapters from the Sixth Assessment Report—Working Group II (AR6/WG2) and Sixth Assessment Report—Working Group III (AR6/WG3) along with the SYR have highlighted climate justice as a key principle within mitigation and adaptation strategies. Climate justice concerns have emerged because of the loss and damage from climate hazards affecting mainly poorer and vulnerable people who have contributed very little to overall greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The success of adaptation strategies therefore depends on equitable development and climate justice. See the section “The IPCC Reports, Digital Publishing, and Climate Justice” in the article for more details.

Associated terms and dictionary creation

Figure 6. Creation of the climate justice word list (Graphviz [source file](#))

Associated climate justice terms in Europe PMC and IPCC

The list of words/terms that appeared in the literature for climate justice in Europe PMC and the IPCC reports has been extracted with docanalysis and keyword extractor. The list of words was checked by the research operators to keep relevant words or phrases and to remove false positives.

Note: The word lists have been extracted from IPCC AR6/WG2/Chapter 08, IPCC AR6/WG2/Chapter 18, and the scholarly literature corpus of 100 articles that mention climate justice.

- **“Word list 100 articles – 25 terms”:** Climate justice–related terms in Europe PMC 100 articles from 2010 to 2024—list of terms from scholarly literature corpus (Europe PMC):

[words_from_lit_corpus.txt](#)

“Word list IPCC report – 51 terms”: Climate justice–related terms from the IPCC AR6/WG2 Report—Chapters [08](#) and [18](#):

[words_IPCC_chao08_chap18.txt](#)

Links to #semanticClimate HTML versions of AR6/WG2 Report—Chapters 08 and 18

- IPCC/AR6/WG2/Chapter 08:
https://html-preview.github.io/?url=https://github.com/petermr/amilib/blob/main/test/resources/ipcc/cleaned_content/wg2/Chapter08/html_with_ids.html
- IPCC/AR6/WG2/Chapter 18:
https://html-preview.github.io/?url=https://github.com/petermr/amilib/blob/main/test/resources/ipcc/cleaned_content/wg2/Chapter18/html_with_ids.html

Creation of the Climate Justice Dictionary

The dictionary has been created from the list of words from the literature corpus and the IPCC reports (see Figure A6). The following is the list of terms used to make the Climate Justice Dictionary.

- **“Word list: Climate Justice Dictionary – 76 terms”:** Terms related to climate justice and including “climate justice” from literature corpus and the IPCC reports:

[words_all_climatejustice.txt](#)

Search IPCC Glossary using Climate Justice Dictionary

The list of words used to make the Climate Justice Dictionary has been compared with the IPCC Glossary terms, and we observed the occurrence of the terms “climate justice” and “Indigenous Peoples” in the glossary. These were the only two terms to appear in the IPCC Glossary from our Climate Justice Dictionary. Such a result is important in a number of ways; for example, it can highlight the possible inclusion of other terms in a glossary but also shows how related terms can be used to indicate the meaning of a section of text.

The dictionary was then further enriched with the information available in Wikipedia, Wikidata, and Wiktionary (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Flow diagram for creating a dictionary from word lists (Graphviz [source file](#))

Wikipedia-enhanced dictionary

As climate science–related terms are not always easily understandable by laypersons, the information in the Climate Justice Dictionary has been added to every word/term from Wikipedia (see Figure A8). The Wikipedia-enhanced dictionary for all the terms was created with the tool `amilib` using the following code.

```
amilib DICT --words words_all_climatejustice.txt --description  
wikipedia --figures --dict climatejustice_dictionary.html --operation  
create
```

search term: Climate justice [Wikipedia Page](#)

Climate justice is a type of [environmental justice](#)^[1] that focuses on the unequal [impacts of climate change](#) on marginalized or otherwise vulnerable populations.^[2] Climate justice seeks to achieve an equitable distribution of both the burdens of [climate change](#) and the efforts to [mitigate climate change](#).^[3] The [economic burden of climate change mitigation](#) is estimated by some at around 1% to 2% of [GDP](#).^{[4][5]} Climate justice examines concepts such as [equality](#), [human rights](#), [collective rights](#), [justice](#) and the historical responsibilities for climate change.^[6]

[Fridays for Future](#) demonstration in Berlin in September 2021 with the slogan "fight for climate justice".

search term: social justice [Wikipedia Page](#)

This is an accepted version of this page

An artist's rendering of what Plato might have looked like. From Raphael's early 16th century painting "Scuola di Atene".

search term: urban migration [Wikipedia Page](#)

Urbanization (or **urbanisation** in [British English](#)) is the population shift from [rural](#) to [urban areas](#), the corresponding decrease in the proportion of people living in rural areas, and the ways in which societies adapt to this change. It can also mean population growth in urban areas instead of rural ones.^[1] It is predominantly the process by which [towns](#) and [cities](#) are formed and become larger as more people begin living and working in central areas.^[2]

Figure 8. Wikipedia-enhanced dictionary for climate justice–associated terms [as web page](#) from text dictionary: [Words_all_climatejustice.txt](#)

The Climate Justice Dictionary:

Climate Justice Dictionary (work in progress): [Words_all_climatejustice.txt](#)

Climate Justice Dictionary (Wikipedia enhanced): [as web page](#)

Supplementary material

1. Europe PMC semi-automated literature search [Jupyter Notebook](#) “Climate Justice Demo #semanticClimate Tools”
2. About #semanticClimate Notebook
<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1WUP8lUKvMV14LiOGSvrDMk9k0Oknd9rk>
3. Literature search
https://github.com/semanticClimate/JEP-article/tree/main/literature_search2010-2024
4. Figures Graphviz source (all files)
<https://github.com/semanticClimate/JEP-article/tree/main/graphviz>
5. Word lists for creating the Climate Justice Dictionary
<https://github.com/semanticClimate/JEP-article/tree/main/data>
6. Dictionaries (drug, diseases, country, virus, etc.)
<https://github.com/petermr/dictionary/tree/main/openVirus20210120>

References

All citations stored here as open citations on Zotero group tagged as #cjd:

<https://www.zotero.org/groups/2437020/semanticclimate/collections/KD8WW5YA/tags/cjd/collectio>

[n](#)

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- IPCC. n.d. *About the IPCC*. Accessed 4 December 2024. <https://www.ipcc.ch/about/>.
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